

POLICY RESEARCH

REPORT

Urban food environments during the COVID-19 pandemic

Public food markets, food security and poor households in Quito, Ecuador

Policy Research Report

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This study is part of the project “Building back better: Using a disruptive crisis to achieve sustainable and gender inclusive improvements in food security, labor markets and social protection in Latin American countries”, implemented by Grupo de Análisis para el Desarrollo de Perú (GRADE), with funding from the International Development Research Centre (IDRC) of Canada.

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Executive Summary

This report analyzes changes in food access and the role of public food markets in Quito (Ecuador) in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. Prior to the health emergency, 52% of the urban population and 65% of poor and vulnerable households acquired most of their food in public food markets. However, the pandemic and biosecurity measures altered the food purchasing pattern. During compulsory confinement, only 17% of households still bought most of their food from markets. As a consequence, other types of establishments, such as supermarkets, mom-and-pop stores and green-grocers, increased their share when a considerable number of urban households were forced to change their usual food sources.

Once the confinement was over, public food markets partially recovered their customers, although the 35% figure indicated that they were still far from recovering completely. Thus, the current situation of the markets is marked by a significant loss of customers, sales volume and even traders, who have abandoned their stalls since the pandemic. In short, the pandemic brought a profound transformation in the food-purchasing pattern.

Still, the pandemic is not the only cause of the ongoing situation of Quito's public food markets. For, as several previous studies indicate, the Municipality of Quito, the governing body, has abandoned them in administrative, institutional, financial and

commercial infrastructure terms. Over the last three decades, Quito's public food markets have had to face marginalization, in addition to i) a more competitive commercial environment due to the proliferation of supermarket chains and small-scale family stores, and ii) technological and logistical changes, as well as changes in the food-purchasing pattern. The weakening of the public market system in Quito contrasts, though, with a number of advantages: fresh food sales; capillary distribution in a large part of the built environment; capacity to absorb the heterogeneous and dispersed production of family and peasant agriculture; and creation of a setting of small urban family businesses, particularly for women and indigenous population.

These characteristics are highly relevant in the context of the global challenge to build sustainable and inclusive agrifood systems.¹ Hence, it is argued that public food markets should be considered and reimagined as a crucial element of urban food planning. It is proposed to strengthen, expand and promote the system of public food markets in order to (re)constitute them as public food centralities focused on i) improving access, availability and affordability of fresh food, ii) establishing sustainable production systems managed by family and peasant agriculture, and iii) being a source of employment for small and medium scale traders and producers.

1 Quito is one of the signatory cities of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFFP).

Research Problem

The pandemic caused by Covid-19 had a strong impact on the food-purchasing pattern in the city of Quito, Ecuador. In the course of the confinement, most public food markets had to close and their clientele were forced to find other establishments to purchase food. Although commercial dynamics have improved since the end of the sanitary emergency, markets remain in a critical situation.

The first central finding is that the weakened state of Quito's public food markets prevented the local government and the urban population from taking advantage of the potential of these commercial sites during the pandemic, unlike other cities and their more successful markets.¹

The second central finding is that the pandemic-generated crisis in public food markets is but another moment in a long-standing trajectory of decline and marginalization. Since the 1990s, the number of markets and their distribution in the urban territory stagnated, despite the continued urban population growth. Renovation and investment in commercial infrastructure and logistics has been practically nonexistent. The governing institution of the market system and the corresponding governance processes have been gradually weakened and replaced by clientelistic and informal relationships. Added to this is the absence of a long-term public policy that considers the fundamental role of public markets in aspects such as food security and recommended diets for urban population, self-employment, supply of services at neighborhood level, economic dynamization of surrounding areas, and construction of social fabric in neighborhoods, among others.

The two findings have important implications for the global challenge of building sustainable and inclusive agrifood systems. It is argued that public food markets should be considered and reimagined as a crucial element of urban food planning. It is proposed to strengthen, expand and promote the system of public food markets, in order to (re)constitute them as food centralities focused on i) improving access, availability and affordability of fresh food, ii) primarily produced through sustainable production systems managed by family and peasant agriculture, and iii) constituting a source of employment for small and medium scale traders and producers.

This report is based on the research project "Agrifood System of Quito", financed by IDRC and carried out in cooperation with GRADE-Peru and FARO, Ecuador. The project consisted of two phases. The first phase involved a diagnosis of food access and the role of public food markets in Quito (Ecuador) in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. The second phase developed an initiative to support a municipal market in order to boost good governance and thus contribute to its commercial reactivation.

The results and recommendations arising from the research project are presented below. The first section describes the recent development of Quito's food ambience. The second section discusses how the pattern of food purchasing was transformed before, during and after the pandemic. The third section focuses on the public management of public food markets in the context of the health emergency. The fourth section analyzes the broader governance context of public food markets. The final section sets out public policy recommendations.

1 Although there are few reports that identify and analyze the fundamental role of markets and fairs in the pandemic framework, some papers offer a very fruitful analysis (Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition, 2021; HealthBridge, 2022; UN-Habitat, 2020, 2022).

The Commercial Dynamics of Quito's Food Environment

The urban food environment of the Metropolitan District of Quito comprised 2.7 million people before the pandemic, who purchased their food items in public food markets (55), mom-and-pop stores and greengrocers (2,242), supermarket chain stores (104) (Hollenstein, 2021; Núñez and Ramírez, 2018), thousands of street vendors, and other establishments, such as bakeries and *bodegas* (shops that function as storage and sales point). This set of commercial actors has been constituted and transformed over time, particularly since the 1990s: while public food markets lost their central role as suppliers, supermarket chains and mom-and-pop stores quickly emerged, offering, above all, processed and ultra-processed foods, as well as greengrocers, specialized in fresh foods. The pandemic affected Quito's food setting in many organizational, economic and social aspects. Although the overall availability and the diversity of the food supply did not suffer a systemic disruption, the pandemic did bring problems of accessibility, access and affordability, for broad social groups, particularly poor and vulnerable households (HPV, in Spanish). So, according to data from this research, 47% of HPV had to reduce the number of meals served per day, 40% developed practices such as cooking with relatives, and 26% produced its own food.

Public food markets were important food centralities for the urban population until the last decade of the 20th century (Hollenstein, 2021). Currently, there are 55 retail public food markets, although two have a mixed profile, that is, they operate at wholesale and retail level (Map 1).¹ As shown in Figure 1, public food markets have traditionally been characterized by offering fresh food of vegetable (48% of the market stalls) and animal (19%) origin, as well as typical prepared dishes (26%) (Hollenstein, 2021).

At present, approximately 12,000 traders work in the city's public food markets, in addition to a large number of loaders and tricycle drivers, aides who thresh grains, etc. The vast majority of traders are women (77%), with a propensity to be in vulnerable socioeconomic situations (heads of household with economically dependent family members). Second, the number of traders who self-identify as indigenous is high (26%) when compared to the national average (6.4%) (INEC, 2020). Finally, the universe of traders is on average older than in other economic sectors.

Starting in the 1990s, the municipal market system entered a phase of stagnation. The number of markets and their distribution in the urban territory came to a standstill after two decades (1970-1980) of continuous and vertiginous growth. Since the end of the 20th century, renovation and public investment in commercial infrastructure and logistics has been practically non-existent, except for occasional restorations. Throughout this time, investment was increasingly assumed by the merchants' associations, despite the fact that they have no formal role in the municipal market system. Finally, the governing institution of the market system and the corresponding governance processes have been gradually weakened and replaced by clientelistic and informal relationships.

Simultaneously, supermarket chains began to expand rapidly, first in middle- and upper-class residential areas, and then, via lower-priced retail formats, in residential neighborhoods characterized by a lower purchasing power. From 17 stores in 1990, supermarket chains expanded to 104 retail

1 The mixed trade centers are Mercado San Roque and Mercado Mayorista de Quito.

Figure 1.
Distribution of Market Stalls by Type of Food/Commodity

Fuente: Hollenstein (2021).

and wholesale supermarkets in 2019, representing a growth of 511%. In the same period, the number of greengrocers expanded from 592 in 1990 to 2,242 in 2017, corresponding to an increase of 270 % (Núñez and Ramírez, 2018). Greengrocers are both a competition to smaller neighborhood markets, as well as clients of the larger public food markets. This type of food source, often managed on a one-person or family basis, extends the supply of fresh plant-based food in a capillary manner all over Quito. In the case of supermarkets, however, the competition is more intense and direct, as they seek to operate by vertically integrated supply chains, separated from the public food markets.² This situation was aggravated by the prolonged pandemic crisis, which was accompanied by a more far-reaching economic crisis. During this period, the competitive spiral among the supermarket chains intensified considerably, with the emergence of new discounter-type formats, whose

offer focuses on processed and ultra-processed foods with increasingly lower prices. At the same time, informal commerce in the outskirts of public food markets soared.

So, changes in Quito's food environment have created a critical situation for public food markets. Nonetheless, the smaller markets have been weak-end more than the intermediate and large ones, due to the wider supply and lower prices that the latter can offer. This situation of unequal commercial slowdown is expressed in a concentration of the number of stalls in the larger markets, while the smaller have fewer and fewer traders or are forced to close completely (Table 1).

Despite the multiple difficulties mentioned above, most public food markets have so far survived. One explanation for this resilience lies in their internal economic life, composed of countless small ventures, often organized as single-person or family units, highly flexible, frequently constituted outside

² Markets lose between 1.4% and 2% of the demanding population per year, according to a study commissioned by the Municipality of Quito (Urbana Consultores, 2015; cited in Hollenstein and Red de Saberes, 2019).

Map 1.
Public food markets in Quito, Ecuador

Source: Based on Hollenstein (2021).

of labor and tax legislation, and with a minimum of fixed and administrative costs.

In sum, several factors have caused the commercial decline and loss of relevance in the food setting of public food markets. The factors that have intensified the competitive environment are 1) the gradual loss of customers, particularly those with greater purchasing power; 2) the change in purchasing patterns towards ultra-processed and cheaper foods, implicit in the expansion of supermarket chains; 3) the technological changes, such as deferred payment and credit, by electronic means; 4) the rise of delivery services, some close-

ly integrated with supermarket chains; and 5) the increase in street vending and the proliferation of mom-and-pop stores, oftentimes in the vicinity of public food markets. From the governance side, the factors affecting the municipal market system are 6) the stagnation of the number of municipal commercial spaces for three decades, despite the growth of the urban population; 7) the deinstitutionalization of the municipal regulatory body; and 8) the absence of a food policy for the city. In this sense, there has been no policy that considers markets as the axis of Quito's agri-food system and the other economic, social and cultural services deriving from it.

Table 1.
Distribution of market stalls in big and small public food markets

	Market stalls (%)	
	1984	2017
5 biggest markets	38,9	54,4
10 smallest markets	8,6	1,2

Source: Based on Hollenstein (2021).

The Transformation of the Food-Purchasing Pattern Before, During and After the Lockdown

The research analyzed the pattern of food purchasing (PCA, in Spanish) via a representative survey in six sectors of the city, characterized by a greater presence of poor and vulnerable households (HPV, in Spanish). Each selected sector has a municipal market, although of different size. A considerable transformation of the PCA was found throughout the pandemic. The surveyed households were forced to change the preferred site of food purchase, usually public food markets, to other types of establishments, such as mom-and-pop stores. In addition, there are substantial differences when disaggregating the overall PCA by sociodemographic variables, such as gender and age.

During the pandemic, the availability of food and the diversity of the food supply may have been affected in terms of breadth of food supply and accessibility of certain products, but the city did not suffer a systemic disruption of food provision. Instead, the pattern of food transactions in the urban territory was strongly affected: supermarket chains served the public without interruption, while traders from public food markets moved to the neighborhoods with trucks, street vendors and newly opened stores. Paradoxically, small and medium-scale farmers faced greater logistical problems to continue supplying the city or to take advantage of opportunities generated by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The conducted survey differentiated three moments: before (M1), during (M2) and after (M3) confinement.¹ During confinement, 56% of the HPVs changed their preferred place of food purchasing. After mandatory confinement ended, 32% of the HPVs did so. The most relevant changes in the PCA were the following (Figure 2): before the pandemic (M1), 51% of HPV purchased most of their food in public food markets, followed by supermarket chains (31%). Neighborhood stores took 10% in the PCA, while other establishments (micro-markets, bodegas, street vendors, etc.) partook of 7%.

In the course of the confinement (M2), the importance of markets was drastically reduced (17%), while mom-and-pop stores increased their participation to 45%. Like mom-and-pop stores during the confinement, street vendors and trucks were able to increase their sales considerably to 18%. In contrast, the importance of supermarket chains was reduced to 20%. Here it is important to note that the focus on poor and vulnerable households brought on particular results, because on a citywide scale, the participation of supermarket chains did not decrease, but increased.

After the confinement (Moment 3), markets managed to recover some of their commercial leverage (35%), as did supermarket chains (22%). On the other hand, mom-and-pop stores lost some of their newly acquired strength, dropping from 45% to 29%. Other food sources, such as street vendors and trucks, also declined.

Sociodemographic variables differentiate this general picture. The most marked variation is due to the age of the household shopper. Younger people shopped 37% in markets before confinement, but older households shopped 70%. Yet, during confinement, markets lost weight in all age groups. Although less notable, another differentiation is that men tended to shop more frequently in super-

¹ The key date is March 19, 2020 (onset). As of July 2020, a traffic light system was introduced to distinguish different scenarios according to the number of cases.

Figure 2.
Transformation of the food purchasing pattern before, during, and after the lockdown

Source: Household survey.

markets than women, who were prone to buy more frequently in markets. Similarly, it was identified that the more income a household had, the more important supermarkets were in the PCA.

The relative importance of markets as a place for HPV food provision also depended on the area of residence of the surveyed households. In the Chiri-yacu market, one of the largest and best organized

throughout the pandemic (see next section), the purchase rate dropped from 59% before to 36% in the confinement. In the Roldós market, a very small commercial site that did not receive support from the Municipality, the respective rates were 44% and 11%. In other words, the pandemic situation affected the markets very differently.

Public Management of Markets During the Pandemic

The pandemic affected public food markets more negatively than any other type of commercial establishment in Quito (see Section 1). The research shows that the state of emergency reinforced a series of limitations on the orderly operation of public food markets, a product of the critical state inherited from previous decades. In short, markets were not prepared to adapt quickly and effectively to the pandemic. Various forms of restrictions made it difficult to serve the clientele on a massive scale. The primary issue emerged following the mandatory closure of most public food markets, which, in turn, generated a critical economic situation for women traders, many of them from poor or vulnerable socioeconomic sectors. A considerable number of traders, especially those of advanced age, never reopened their market stalls. Another group of traders set up their own businesses in the form of mom-and-pop stores or greengrocers.

From the beginning of the pandemic, the National Emergency Operations Committee (COE-N, in Spanish) warned municipalities that they should implement mechanisms for the organization and control of markets to guarantee the supply and to avoid price rise. This task was often difficult to achieve, given that public food markets had been operating since before the pandemic with organizational and institutional difficulties (see Section 1). The response to this situation was a combination of several strategies, from seeking to implement a series of restrictions to guarantee the internal commercial organization of the markets, such as reduction of the allowed capacity, social distancing, mandatory use of masks and gloves, schedule changes and other forms of limiting consumer access, to issuing authoritarian warnings from the mayor's office: "we will not tremble if we have to close all the markets" (El Comercio, 2020).

However, despite these measures, infection rates among the traders and the population of surrounding neighborhoods rose very rapidly, prompting the COE-N and the Municipality of Quito to close many markets (Figure 3) two weeks after decreeing the state of sanitary emergency. Subsequently, the number of open markets was rapidly reduced from 55 (before the pandemic) to 12 in mid-April 2020, representing a 78% reduction of food supply from

these types of establishments. This is reflected in the survey data: 76% of the surveyed households indicated that the market where they used to shop was closed during the confinement.

The closure of the markets was only completely reversed at the end of October 2020. During this time, the Municipality of Quito sought to create alternative spaces, such as food fairs, though these were established late and not in the quantities and frequencies required to fill the void that emerged from the closure of the public food markets.

At the same time, corporate establishments, such as supermarket chains, but also mom-and-pop stores and greengrocers, were clearly more effective and quicker in establishing and controlling biosecurity measures among their employees and clientele.

The closure of the public food markets was a significant milestone. Ninety-nine percent of the surveyed households indicated that these commercial sites are very important for food purchasing, regardless of whether they do most of their food shopping there or not. In addition, 73% of households revealed that the closure highly affected food access. The main difficulties faced by HPVs to stock up on food were the closure of preferred shopping site (91%), lack of transportation (76%), higher prices at new provision places (74%), and greater distance to new sites (57%). The main reasons HPVs reported

Figure 3.
Evolution of the number of markets open during the lockdown period

Source: Fieldwork.

not continuing to shop at markets during confinement were non-compliance with biosecurity mea-

sures (70%); distance between home and preferred market (15%); and lack of cash (10%).

Public Market Governance: Navigating Uncertainty

During the pandemic, most markets could not stay open and were unable to fulfill their role as food suppliers for the urban population. Nevertheless, even in this discouraging context, there were some markets that did not have to close in the critical phase or that were affected to a lesser degree by the decrease in clientele and the abandonment of stalls. This heterogeneity among public food markets is explained by aspects such as their size: it is more difficult to close a very large market, that functions as a pillar of the urban agri-food system, than a small neighborhood market. However, this research also showed that there is another aspect that influenced the trajectory and commercial dynamics of the markets during the sanitary emergency: the internal governance process. In other words, how, by whom and at what time decisions were made significantly influenced the performance of public food markets throughout and after the pandemic.

As mentioned, at the beginning of the pandemic, public food markets did not have the internal organization nor the public institutionality that would allow them to play a crucial role in supplying Quito's neighborhoods. Thus, the implementation and control of biosecurity measures were, in effect, very complicated to achieve. As a result, they were exposed to private and corporate competition, which managed to overcome these difficulties more effectively and efficiently.

Despite this generalized context, there were significant differences in the management of specific situations in each of the public food markets studied. The investigation yielded three scenarios. In the first, markets and fairs were barely affected by the pandemic: the closure did not last long; the reopening process was carried out according to a formally set up procedure, and the number of traders and customers was similar to that before the pandemic (Chiriyacu and Carapungo markets).

The second scenario, more critical, includes markets with loss of traders and those that had to face longer closures (Guamaní and San Roque markets). The third scenario, of destabilizing type, occurred when the number of traders decreased drastically and the duration of the closure was also prolonged (Calderón and Roldós markets).

The research showed that the differentiated scenarios faced by the markets were rooted in the char-

acteristics of the internal governance process of each market. Basically, the determining factor was who made by which means what kind of decision: decisions and actions of market administrators, boards and representatives (presidents, associations) of merchants, municipal officials. Moreover, it was crucial how these different actors interacted. As a whole, the heterogeneous expression of these aspects explains why certain markets never closed, some reopened early and others had to face a prolonged period of closure. The detailed situation of each market is shown in Table 2.

The finding that internal organizational and decision-making processes play an important role in commercial dynamics opened up the possibility of formulating a concrete initiative to promote good governance in public food markets (Box 1). The main motivation for the initiative was as follows: improving governance practices would have a positive impact on the commercial dynamics of the markets, which, in turn, would benefit the food security of poor and vulnerable households in the vicinity of the municipal market. The promotion initiative that was developed in the second phase of the research project based on this rationale is described in more detail in Box 1.

Table 2.
Situation and factors that influenced internal governance during the emergency in the six public food markets studied

	Stable Scenario		Unstable Scenario		Critical Scenario	
	Chiriyacu Market	Carapungo Market	Guamaní Market	San Roque Market	Roldós Market	Calderón Market
Duration of closure	Never closed	6 weeks	8 weeks	10 weeks	10 weeks	9 weeks
Reopening process	Does not apply	Regulated	Regulated	Chaotic, unregulated	Regulated	Regulado
Tendency number of traders	Estabilidad relativa	Estabilidad relativa	Pérdida de comerciantes	Pérdida de comerciantes	Pérdida de comerciantes	Reducción drástica
Customer dynamics	-14 %	-18 %	-18 %	+3 %	-19 %	-18 %

Factors influencing the internal governance process	
Chiriyacu Market	Very large, organized market, with a high level of management and leadership to develop and implement an innovative closure and reopening plan; sufficient political weight, administrative support and systemic relevance to stay open.
Carapungo Market	Intermediate market, highly organized by an association with clear leadership; very orderly market.
Mercado Guamaní	Intermediate fair, vulnerable due to the lack of support and conflictive relation with the Municipality of Quito; divided leadership into two associations; infrastructure that hinders pandemic management.
Mercado San Roque	Very large market, with conflictive internal relations; several opposing interests among a high number of associations; no consolidated leadership; politicized market; questioned by the Municipality of Quito.
Mercado Roldós	Very small market, with conflictive social relations; absence of leadership and lack of support from ACDC.
Mercado Calderón	Newly built market, in a very vulnerable situation; internal management of associations is weak; depends on the personal effort of the market's management; important support from the administrator during confinement; organization of the market's external space is highly difficult due to the presence of street vendors.

Source: Fieldwork.

Box 1.**Pilot intervention to revitalize trade in public food markets**

The second phase of the project was based on the finding that the situation of a particular market depended not only on “higher” governance levels, but also on “internal” factors. Hence, a pilot initiative was proposed in the Calderon market, with the aim of creating and strengthening more transparent decision-making mechanisms, based on dialogue and collective agreements. As noted, the hypothesis was that good market governance would eventually have a positive effect on trade dynamics, without the need to first transform the formal governance framework and higher levels (see Figure 4).

The intervention chosen was the development and implementation of a commercial and marketing strategy for the Calderón market, as a pilot market. To this end, a new figure of interaction and coordination was created to take advantage of the Calderón market’s recent experience in testing new modalities of internal organization. The Calderón Market Marketing and Development Commission (COMYD, in Spanish) was conceived as a multi-stakeholder platform, made up of representatives of the market’s merchants, the District Trade Coordination Agency and actors outside the market, i.e., FARO and a marketing specialist company (Ubuntu).

The main axis of the intervention consisted of designing and implementing a marketing strategy to reposition the Calderón market as an attractive food supply site. In addition, two commercial reactivation strategies related to the marketing strategy were developed: the sale of baskets of fresh food and groceries, and the

implementation of a coupon system so customers could claim a series of promotions in different market segments. A third element of the strategy was the technical training of COMYD members by Ubuntu and, later, the training of a larger group of Calderón market’s merchants by COMYD itself. A fourth element was the development of an application manual to replicate the entire intervention in other public food markets.

The creation of COMYD succeeded in decentralizing the decision-making process, as well as in elaborating and carrying out initiatives that were self-financed by the merchants. The COMYD developed new strategies to reactivate the market in commercial terms and radiate a new way of “being” and “doing the market”. It even succeeded in devising strategies to raise its own funding. Though, the new entity faced a number of difficulties, such as additional unpaid workload, absence at the stalls, difficulties to establish transparent and inclusive communication channels, as well as lack of funds to continue with the marketing campaigns on the Facebook fanpage.

In sum, the initiative confirmed that there are opportunities to consolidate and improve good governance. Nonetheless, it also demonstrated that internal governance processes depend on other levels of governance, as the municipal market system and its regulatory entity (the District Trade Coordination Agency), public policies at city level (urban planning, land use, food and health) and division of competencies among different state entities at national level (Ministry of Agriculture vs. Municipality of Quito).

Policy Recommendations

The recent history of public food markets shows a growing marginalization in the food consumption patterns of the urban population. The pandemic was an additional event that had a negative impact on their commercial dynamics and, therefore, on the food security of poor and vulnerable households in Quito. At the same time, the data presented in this report indicate that, for the urban population, particularly for poor and vulnerable households, they continue to be highly important sources of food supply, particularly for fresh food. An uninterrupted weakening trajectory has had far-reaching consequences for the popular commercial economy operating in public food markets in the form of thousands of small family businesses, often led by women. Concurrently, the weakening of public food markets is likely to have negatively affected the already few and precarious commercialization channels of peasant family farming.

The findings presented in this report have fundamental implications in the context of the global

challenge of building sustainable and inclusive agri-food systems. It is argued that public food markets should be considered and reimagined as a crucial element of urban food planning. Consequently, it is proposed to strengthen, expand and promote the system of public food markets in order to (re)constitute them as public food centralities focused on i) improving access, availability and affordability of fresh food; ii) establishing sustainable production systems managed by family and peasant agriculture, and iii) constituting a source of employment for small and medium scale traders and producers.

In this way, public food markets can take advantage of their potential to contribute to the construction of an urban agrifood system that is i) resilient to shocks, such as the pandemic, ii) sustainable in terms of production systems (agroecological, organic) and local origin of food, iii) diverse in terms of variety of food offered, and iv) inclusive in economic, social and cultural terms. For this objective to be possible, the following steps must be addressed.

- **Reform institutions that regulate the governance of public food markets, in order to fill governance gaps among different levels of government and include all relevant stakeholders in the process of market management and administration, especially traders' organizations.**
- **Increase public investment in public food markets as part of the strategy to improve food security and public health by enhancing availability, access, affordability and food safety in the procurement and consumption of fresh and minimally processed foods.**
- **Develop innovative management models that i) diversify the supply and the services of public food markets, without diminishing their primary function as food centrality; ii) are based on new alliances between the public sector and the popular and solidarity economy sector; iii) link public food markets with stakeholders, such as associations of producers and the family and peasant agriculture sector, government entities, schools, hospitals, non-governmental organizations and international cooperation; iv) are adapted to the diversity of markets (differentiated according to size, supply profile, scale of trade, etc.), and v) make it possible to develop strategies for the promotion and marketing of public food markets.**

- **Recognize the systemic nature of all markets (mixed, retail), fairs and municipal platforms and their capillary operation through their close commercial relations with greengrocers.**
- **Acknowledge trade organizations as central actors in the municipal market system.**
- **Encourage inclusion and collaboration between public food markets, producer associations and alternative food networks, particularly agroecological fairs.**
- **Boost the multifunctionality of public food markets by incorporating public services and services in general, local cultural offer and spaces to foster entrepreneurship.**
- **Promote public health through their certification as Healthy Markets in accordance with current regulations.**

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